

Towards Multi-Pbps Backbone Optical Networks in Support of Future 6G Networks

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Abstract: We describe innovative concepts associated with optical switching nodes and their transceiver interfaces that enable energy-efficient flexible capacity scaling (≥ 10 Tb/s per interface, ≥ 1 Pb/s capacity per link and ≥ 10 Pb/s throughput per node). © 2024 The Author(s)

1. Introduction

Mobile traffic segment continues growing at an exponential rate of 30-40% per year due to emerging applications and new use cases, resulting in a demand surge for higher capacities at the underlying wireless and optical x-haul infrastructures. This leads the research community to investigate novel solutions related to effective transport of wireless traffic over an optical xhaul infrastructure, due to its inherent ultra-high capacity and energy-efficiency. In that framework, recently, there have been research proposals associated with the possible deployment of Space Division Multiplexing (SDM) based optical links (e.g., utilizing bundles of standard-single-mode fibers) and Ultra-Wide Band (UWB) transmission systems (e.g., over S+C+L bands). However, besides upgrading the transmission systems, there is also a need to enhance the capabilities of the associated optical switching systems which enable bypassing of power-hungry Hierarchy Level IP routers (HL1-4) across the x-haul. It is envisioned that sometime in the future, network operation will transition to the utilization of waveband switching and even full-spectrum fiber switching, as opposed to today's wavelength switching. To support a smooth migration towards such future network operation, there have been proposals for the utilization of Multi-Granular Switching Nodes (MG-ONs) employing novel WaveBand Selective Switches (WBSSs) to efficiently handle the spatial and spectral resources of the network [1-2].

In this article, we describe a flexible waveband switching paradigm utilizing an innovative Photonic Integrated Circuit (PIC)-based flex-WBSS, as well as the novel ultra-high-rate transceiver interfaces of such UWB/SDM nodes that are being developed in the framework of the EC-Funded R&D project FLEX-SCALE [3].

2. Novel x-haul Network Architecture and Technology Innovations

We envision a future energy-efficient and capacity-scalable converged packet-optical transport architecture, to provide back-haul connectivity in a disaggregated 6G network. It will integrate the IP packet nodes (e.g., access, aggregation, and core routers) with a multi-granular and flexible optical transport layer composed of Pb/s-scale UWB/SDM optical transmission links and multi-Pb/s optical switching nodes. These multi-Pb/s throughput MG-ONs are being implemented by the FLEX-SCALE consortium, to achieve (i) flexible waveband to full fiber switching with novel WBSSs using route and select (R&S) architecture, (ii) add and drop using Optical Cross Connects (OXC)s, and (iii) wavelength switching using conventional Wavelength Selective Switches (WSSs) [4]. The MG-ONs at this converged IP/optical architecture allow traffic to optimally bypass intermediate power-hungry IP/packet routers by deploying among the IP/optical nodes, optical links that can support capacities ranging from individual Tb/s channels to Pb/s optical multiplexed spectral-spatial super-channels.

The interfaces of these nodes, feeding the optical links connecting them, should offer ultra-high rates by combining Tb/s-class single-wavelength, single-fiber I/O transceivers with UWB and SDM multiplexing schemes to achieve Pb/s link capacities. As shown in Fig. 1(a), the UWB/SDM spectral-spatial super-channels are aggregated starting from arrays of our high-rate single-wavelength transmitters (top – Fig. 1a) and are demultiplexed at the receivers' arrays (bottom – Fig. 1a). Significant effort has been focused on the development of optical Digital-to-Analog Converters - DACs (oDACs) [5]. These elements adopt direct Digital-to-Optical conversion, improving the trade-offs between performance, energy-efficiency, complexity, and cost-reduction for optical transmitters (Tx's) by essentially eliminating the power-hungry high-order electronic DACs [5]. The FLEX-SCALE project develops a novel oDAC architecture enabling coherent in-phase optical superposition of multiple optical PAM signals, coming from different $S (=2, 3, \dots)$ parallel branches (paths) of the oDAC Tx, each produced by a properly biased optical Mach Zehnder Modulator (MZM) driven by existing electronic PAM drivers [5]. The resulting optical signals are multi-level PAM- m

($m=2^S=4, 8, 16, \dots$), which can be also orthogonally I-Q multiplexed to generate high quality m^2 -QAM signals with zero modulation loss [5]. The envisioned optical UWB/SDM super-channel would support L spectral lanes and N spatial lanes over a single SDM fiber link (which can be implemented as a bundle of standard single mode fibers). Having e.g., $N \geq 6$ and $L \geq 100$ (assuming utilization of S, C and/or L bands), leads to $L \times N \geq 600$ lanes, that carry >128 GBaud optical signals to bring the raw per-link capacity to over > 1 Pb/s (for coherent transponders also utilizing polarization multiplexing). Considering the roadmap for the expected increase in baud rates, such a system could reach ~ 10 Pb/s capacity by 2030.

The novel WBSS, placed at ingress/egress fibers of the MG-ON architecture, access the entire UWB optical spectrum, carving out flexibly defined, continuous, and flat sub-bands, enabling switching to multiple output ports via a route and select architecture (top - Fig. 1b). The WBSS is implemented on a PIC and can achieve rapid (μ s-order) reconfigurable operation, in terms of switching the different sub-bands (via a $4 \times N$ crossbar switch) to the desired output ports [3]. Being capable of flexibly carving-out wavebands of different sizes, WBSSs can adapt the provisioned band from the size of a spectral super-channel to full-fiber spectrum, hence being able to smoothly support the transition from super-channel switching to full-spectrum fibre-switching scenarios. Band Add/Drop from/to full-band transceivers is accessed in a Colorless / Directionless / Contentionless (C/D/C) manner using an OXC (middle - Fig. 1b). The MG-ONs node architecture supports legacy WSSs at the lowest tier (bottom - Fig. 1b), which are likely to be phased out in the future or remain only at the edge, in support of a cost and power-effective backbone network.

Fig. 1 – (a) UWB/SDM super-channels are aggregated from high-rates single wavelength transmitters (top) to receiver arrays (bottom) (b) MG-ON architecture supporting S+C+L bands with flex-WBSS at fiber ingress/egress ports.

3. Conclusion

We have introduced a novel optical switching architecture based on the efficient exploitation of spectral & spatial resources available in future UWB/SDM based 6G back-haul networks providing ≥ 10 Tb/s per interface, ≥ 1 Pb/s capacity per link and ≥ 10 Pb/s throughput per node.

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